

Beyond the Pill: Solving the Structural Crisis of Drug Therapy

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Currently, more than 70% of visits to the doctor end with the use of drug therapy. In essence, the main method of treatment of modern medicine differs little from the methods of the Middle Ages and the pre-Christian era.

The basis of this method is the dosed administration of certain substances into the body. And these substances, in most cases, are poisons for the human body. And it was agreed that in a certain dosage, these substances are no longer poisons, but medicines. And the volume of global production of these substances is currently more than 1.5 trillion dollars. Any medication is accompanied by a positive effect and some negative, in percentage terms to the positive.

If drug therapy is short-lived, then this method is justified. Problems begin with constant drug therapy or taking medications with a large negative coefficient (the ratio of a negative effect to a positive one). And this negative impact tends to increase and accumulate a cumulative effect. And at some point in time, disaster strikes. Anyone who has experienced chronic or oncological diseases in themselves or their loved ones will understand what we are talking about.

Obviously, in the 21st century, **the method of invasive drug therapy, as the main treatment method, has outlived its usefulness.** Therapeutic effects on the body should be targeted, narrowly focused, without negative, accumulating effects.

When it comes to cancer, this requires the destruction of a specific cancer cell. Biological barriers, poor blood supply, acidity (pH), drug release mechanisms, high intratumor pressure—all these and other obstacles observed during chemotherapy—should not be present. Guaranteed 100% targeted damage, sparing healthy cells.

Pathogenic bacteria and microbes must be destroyed with 100% certainty, despite accumulated antibiotic resistance and other tricks.

Any type of virus, despite its mutation rate and size hundreds of times smaller than bacteria, must be guaranteed to be destroyed once it enters the human body.

What do all these negative phenomena have in common, and what actions are needed to combat them? Any type of virus, bacteria, microbe, or cancer cell is extremely vulnerable to physical impacts in laboratory conditions, such as localized high temperatures, but becomes difficult to reach in the host's body.

It is necessary to combine information scanning, detection, and intervention methods into a single technology.

And unfortunately, without a technological breakthrough in physics (as a science) You can't do without it. And a revolutionary technology can be the method that I called **the process of Selective Action in a 3-dimensional Structure of a substance on a limited area** (hereinafter referred to as SAS). The SAS also includes information scanning. The resolution of this technology for medical purposes should be in the range of 10 microns- 10 nm (400 μm - 0.4 μm). **The technology will make it possible to influence cellular structures of various types and viruses.** There are 600 million cells in 1 cm³(1ml), and one can only imagine what computing power will be required for information processing of this process. And of course, **without AI, this technology cannot exist.** Currently, there are prototypes of SAS technology, such as NMR, CT, and X-ray therapy, but they do not have sufficient resolution and a 3-dimensional exposure method.

One can only imagine what opportunities this technology will provide in the context of medicine:

- **victory over 100% of types of cancer, viruses, bacteria, and microbes.**
- **disabling any kind of pain**
- **guaranteed release from various addictions (for example, drug, alcohol, gambling)**
- **slowing down aging, prolonging life, reproductive engineering**

- regeneration of tissues, bones, teeth, limbs**
- treatment of diseases that were considered incurable (and there are a lot of them)**
- technologies for growing replacement organs both outside and in the patient's body (in parallel with the organ requiring replacement)**
- treatment of genetic diseases and genetic modification**
- great opportunities for implanting various technological improvers, exoskeletons, neuromodules**

Beyond its direct impact on matter, the SAS method will offer tremendous opportunities for studying the human body and diagnosing various conditions. Essentially, the human body is like a microcosm—there are huge gaps in knowledge about its functioning and internal interactions:

- Consciousness and brain function. Mechanisms underlying subjective experience—such as feelings, thoughts, and self-awareness. The functions of sleep, dreaming mechanisms, and their mutual influence on the body. The brain's lymphatic system—a self-cleansing system for removing toxins.
- Mechanisms of neurodegeneration in the body. As life expectancy increases, the number of people with Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases will only increase.
- Mechanisms of autoimmune diseases. There is a problem of increasing incidence of diabetes, multiple sclerosis, and severe allergies.
- Mechanisms of Essential Hypertension. Doctors prescribe medications to regulate blood pressure, but they fail to understand and address the underlying cause, which over time leads to tragic consequences.
- Deep DNA research. Junk DNA research (in fact, 98% of DNA remains unstudied—a huge omission). 3D genome mapping. The mysteries of epigenetics. The list of things insufficiently studied in the context of DNA could go on and on—and the list would be much longer than the list of phenomena studied.

A person can truly become the master of his body.

If this SAS technology is invented, **most of the planet's computing resources will be working to service this technology.**

SAS will become a quantum transition not only in medicine, but also in the entire technological structure of mankind. Learn more about the SAS technology in the following articles.